

DEVELOPING GEN Y THROUGH: WORK VALUES, WORK ENGAGEMENT AND WORK COMMITMENT

ISMI DARMASTUTI

Fakultas Ekonomika dan Bisnis, Universitas Diponegoro, Semarang.

ELDES WILLY FILATROVI

Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi, BANK BPD JATENG, Semarang.

Email: eldeswillyfilatrovi@stiebankbpdjateng.ac.id

Abstract

One of the logo new disturbing conditions for the frame of employees is the amount of Generation Y entering into the frame of employees with unique trends than preceding generations. In the area of work, are often touted as a technology that loves freedom and prefers freedom in have a glance at, work, or enterprise. This technology is likewise identified as task seeker. By 2020-2030, he's projected to obtain 70% of the general Indonesian population (Sebastian, Amran, & Youth Lab, 2016). This can be an asset for the development of Indonesian as they may also control large generations well. Plus, it lets in any enterprise manage their millennial frame of workers. Generation Y to be a pervasive research concern count number worldwide due to the period of manufacturing and the amount of humans agreed upon through manner of manner of this era. It's clearly that just a few Indonesian studies managing Generation Y issues. The for inquiring for this survey early is prepared generations executed countries, now now not continually similar to Generation Y in Indonesia. As for the sample used as many as 200 people. The technique of records assessment applied in is the quantitative assessment technique, this is the technique of assessment form of numbers and calculations the use of statistical techniques. SEM, AMOS are used to simplify the analytical process.

Keywords: Work Values, Work Engagement, Gen Y, Work Commitment

INTRODUCTION

One of the rising demanding situations in the global of labor is the massive variety of Generation Y who generally to input the arena of labor with distinct traits than preceding generations. In the workplace, are regularly touted as that prefers freedom and flexibility as heaps as freedom from study, art work and business. This generation is also noted as venture seekers. From 2020 to 2030, Indonesia is projected to gain her 70% of the whole working-age population (Sebastian, Amran and Youth Lab, 2016). This may be an asset for Indonesia's monetary machine and improvement if are nicely managed as a big range of generations. However, research on Generation Y in Indonesia. The purpose this observe preceding research on Generation Y achieved the US and one in all locations do not normally fit the traits of Generation Y. One of the motives is the arrival of global facts in Indonesia. Information arriving through the Internet has just arrived in Indonesia and one in all a type advanced international locations have extended felt the impact of the Internet. The lifestyles and improvement of the international affects the charge of the modern-day era.

Today, Generation Y poses a project for the commercial enterprise international as they start to input the hard work market. Generation Y, born among 1980 and 2000, is visible as era

freedom to pick out what fits them, which include free desire of jobs. Different generations the place of regularly create multiple group of interior an organization(Sajjadi, Sun, & Castillo, 2012).Studying the mistakes and successes ofprevious generations is essential in mitigating problems which can stand up withinside theplace of job and can be used to advantage organizational goals more efficiently.Angeline (2011) compares the art work of Dries et al. (2008) and Zemke et al.(2000), Generation Y is seen as well-performing, more supportive, and more positive about the future in comparison to infant boomers and Generation X. Theydo now no longer like strict surveillance approaches or strict walking hours. Millennials stay longer in jobs and businesses that use advanced technology, challenging jobs, and what they love. This generation is said to simply accept versions and art work-life balance.

In terms of hiring, a study conducted by McCrindle (2006) found that 20.8% of Generation Y got their current job through a recruitment or outsourcing company. Trend towards outsourcing is seen as suitable to meet the wishes of stakeholders and companies looking for work. 20.7% of Generation Y learned about their current job from online job postings. This situation corresponds to characteristics of Generation Y, who are tech-savvy and connected. Millennials are a hot topic worthy of research. Few previous studies , especially in Indonesia, on examining work values increased organizational involvement. Most of the existing research focuses on the differences in traits between generations, so more focused work value this millennial. This study seeks to confirm that Gen Y personalities work values increase organizational engagement.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Work Values

Decide their paintings overall performance. Great paintings overall performance stems from positive, straightforward and may increase organizational productivity. Work values are intently associated with an individual's attitudes, perceptions, and approximately paintings. An organization's achievement relies upon at the price of its paintings. Work values are crucial because they impact organizational behavior, paintings overall performance, productivity, and organizational engagement.

According to Hofstede (1980), work values are individual and attitudes toward one's own work, personal relationships with employees, and loyalty to the company and organization. How employees value their work and how it creates pride, responsibility, integrity work style, and ultimately job performance. It can also be used as a guide for Smola and Sutton (2002), Work value is a measure of evaluation related to work and the work environment that is considered correct or important. Rose et al.(1999, Lyon et al. 2010) said that the price of labor may be described as the relative desirability of diverse components of labor including pay, autonomy and operating conditions, and well known ideals approximately work-associated results including performance.

Work Engagement

Work engagement is the nation where in man or woman is emotionally and intellectually dedicated to enterprise. Work engagement takes place whilst human valued, experience their paintings, and agree with in it. The place of business is conceptualized as individuals of business enterprise gratifying their process role, running and expressing themselves physically, cognitively and emotionally for the duration of their paintings. Kahn (1990), Work Engagement as a shape of optimizing the dedication of organizational individuals to their roles through incorporating physical, cognitive, and emotional dimensions. Emotional. Bakker (2004) describe as an expression of nice paintings-associated mind and fulfillment, an enjoyable enjoy for personnel. This includes emotions of enthusiasm (strength), dedication (dedication) and gratitude (immersion). Another opinion on is nice mindset toward the business enterprise and the values it contains. Engaged personnel are aware commercial enterprise with colleagues to enhance performance for the gain of the business enterprise (Robinson, Perryman, & Hayday, 2004). Bakker & Leiter (2010) agree with that one of the maximum vital elements whilst commercial enterprise businesses face intense marketplace opposition. It is associated with private and corporate overall performance. According to experts, it may be concluded that the company motivates its personnel for his or her involvement through growing nice surroundings and setting up appropriate conversation relationships amongst colleagues.

Generation Y

The idea of generations became first recommend by Karl Mannheim in 1923 in his essay The Problem of Generations. Mannheim (1952) defines a technology as a collection of people born the equal ancient and sociocultural context and having formative and shared experiences. "Distinguishable people sharing delivery year, age, and vast lifestyles activities at key developmental stages (hours) which are 5-7 years of the primary wave. Group (Cohort)", organization and very last organization. Ryder (1965) described a technology as a collection of folks who skilled the equal occasion over a time frame. The phrase technology has traditionally been used to explain a time frame or time sees generations as collections of folks who pick out companies primarily based totally on their delivery year, age, location, of activities of their lives. Generation Y is the organization of humans born among 1980 and 2000.

You are the first technology to develop up with virtual technology. The Internet and social media as a part of our everyday lives. Millennials are typically baby boomers. They are young, educated, and think differently. This generation is not only different from previous generations, but also has a different way of thinking about work and life. Generation Y, or Millennials, is the uniquely characterized generation with the largest workforce today. Understanding their perspectives, characteristics and motivations will help you manage human resources and performance in the workplace.

Work Commitment

Luthans (2011) defines as an individual's sturdy preference to be a part of willingness to attempt and paintings difficult, and in and recognition of values and goals. Therefore, human beings who've organizational dedication have a tendency to illustrate recognition, confidence, and a study attitude toward values and goals. Job Engagement or Job Engagement is described as the extent of enthusiasm of toward the obligations assigned the workplace. It is an individual's experience of obligation to goals, assignment and imaginative and prescient of the with which they may be associated. There are numerous motives why is important.

Vital to permit groups to obtain their desires and stick with their vision. Without a stimulated workforce, groups can lose the whole thing they've earned over the years, consisting of recognize and marketplace position. Employee retention is a real issue, if an agency could make experience valued, it'll lead to more engagement the workplace. But a stimulated and devoted organization of, an agency may be at risk. Commitment to paintings leads to accelerated productivity. Imagine now no longer being devoted to what they are doing at your agency. It's a disaster. Such personnel generally tend to spend their running hours browsing the net for private entertainment or searching for different employment opportunities. This is a waste of time and resources. This is simply one instance and also you cannot blame each employee. However, if an agency does now no longer encourage its personnel and inspire their engagement in their paintings, they may be genuinely much more likely to come to be in the sort of situation.

RESEARCH METHODS

Types of Research

This take a look at is a theoretical or hypothetical quantitative explanatory take a look at to check the phenomenon that occurs (Cooper and Schindler, 2006). Primary information series strategies use surveys which can be sent at once to respondents.

Sample

The population used on this observes is Generation Y, already running in banking centers in Central Java. The quantity of samples is two hundred samples. This meets the minimum pattern requirement for statistical information processing.

Reliability and Validity Test Analysis

A reliability take a look at to check if the survey is still really well worth using. If this system is inconsistent, eligibility may be showed if the Cronbach alpha score, alpha (α), is extra than 0.6 and much less than 0.6 (Singgih, 2000). A look at that tests whether or not the respondent knows the query being asked. A scale is taken into consideration legitimate if the adjusted general object correlation is 0. (Singgih 2000).

Data Analysis Method

SEM, AMOS are used to simplify the analytical manner. The device used to manner the records on this observe is the SEM (Structural Equation Model) operated through AMOS (Analysis of Moment Structure). As defined in Ferdinand (2014), the use of structural equation models (SEM) calls for the subsequent seven steps: (1) conversion flowchart to collection and structural equation version specification measures, (2) enter matrix selection and estimation strategies for the built version, (3) trouble specific assessment, (4) assessment criteria, goodness of fit, and (5) Model interpretation and modification.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This phase describes the descriptive statistics received from the respondents. Descriptive statistics are supplied in studies that profile observe statistics and set up relationships among the variables used observe (Hair et al., 1995).

Respondents by Gender

The composition of respondents by gender dimension can be seen in Table

Table
Respondents by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	98	49.00
Male	112	56.00
Total	200	100.0

Sources: Primary data are processed, 2019

The desk indicates that male respondents constitute the bulk of respondents, or 56.00% of the overall 2 hundred respondents who participated the survey.

Testing Assumptions SEM

Normality

The subsequent check is to test the extent of normality of the statistics used on this study. This check is supposed to take a look at the statistics skewness values used whilst the statistics skewness CR values are extra and much less than 2.

Table

Variable	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
X1	66.67	75.238	.443	.845
X2	66.28	74.042	.451	.845
X3	66.72	74.664	.422	.846
X4	66.22	74.918	.371	.848
X5	66.58	74.685	.471	.844
X6	66.45	75.254	.395	.847
X7	66.50	74.975	.442	.845
X8	66.21	76.361	.318	.850
X9	66.15	74.706	.485	.843
X10	66.17	74.514	.423	.846
X11	66.20	74.622	.464	.844
X12	66.40	75.134	.413	.846
X13	66.39	74.114	.470	.844
X14	66.46	74.509	.413	.846
X15	66.47	75.155	.473	.844
X16	66.44	75.570	.418	.846
X17	66.51	74.895	.437	.845
X18	66.54	75.492	.449	.845
X19	66.44	74.733	.461	.844
X20	66.48	73.664	.515	.842

Source: Research data are processed, 2019

Processing indicates that there is no outlying skewness CR values greater than or less than 2.58. Therefore, it can be said that the use of study data met the data normality requirement or that the study data were normally distributed.

Multivariate Outliers

Multivariate outlier assessment is important due to the fact at the equal time due to the fact the information analyzed confirmed no outliers on the univariate level, observations that may be outliers when combined, the Mahalonobis distance

(Mahalonobis distance), where in the distance from the observation is the not unusual place of all variables withinsidethe multidimensional space(Hair,et al. 1995; Norusis,1994; Tabacnick and Fidel, 1996 in Ferdinand, 2002).Measures Mahalonobis chi-rectangular values primarily based totally definitely surely on smoking depth from20 (index) at the quantity of p

Table
Multivariate Outliers

Observation number	D-squared Mahalanobis	p1	p2
7	34.339	,003	,263
30	29.539	.014	,398
99	27.231	,027	,506
----	---	---	---
----	---	---	---
10	6.871	,961	,249
87	6.540	,969	,183
5	5.851	,982	,165

Source: Research data are processed, 2019

Analysis of Structural Equation Modeling

Subsequent assessment is that of SEM as an entire model after analyzing the levels of the one-dimensional symptoms and symptoms that make up the latent variables tested factor assessment. Analysis of facts processing at whole model SEM diploma for suitability and statistical testing. The table shows the effects processing for SEM assessment of the whole model.

Table
Feasibility Model Testing Results
SEM analysis

Goodness of Fit Index	Cut-off Value	Results Analysis	evaluation Model
Chi - Square	<106.394 df 84	90.194	Well
probability	ϵ 0:05	0,302	Well
RMSEA	δ 0:08	0,027	Well
GFI	ϵ 0.90	0.899	marginal
AGFI	ϵ 0.90	0.856	marginal
CMIN / df	$\leq$ 2.00	1.074	Well
TLI	ϵ 0.95	.987	Well
CFI	ϵ 0.95	0,990	Well

Source: Research data are processed, 2018

Statistical exams of relationships among variables are proposed for use as a foundation for answering studies hypotheses. A look at outcomes from SEM processing performed thinking

about the importance stage of the connection among variables as discovered with the aid of using the probability (p) and vital ratio (CR) values for each dating among variables. The statistical take a look at system is proven in the table

Table
Standardized Regression Weight

Variable			estimate	SE	CR	P	Information
Work Engagement	<-- -	Work Values Intrinsik	,147	,122	2,202	,029	Sig
Work Engagement	<-- -	Work Values Social	,192	,110	2,751	,003	Sig
Work Engagement	<-- -	Work Values Ekstrinsik	,175	,140	2,248	,012	Sig
Work Engagement	<-- -	Work Values Prestise	,027	,125	214	,830	No Sig
Work Commitment	<-- -	Work Engagement	,389	,149	2,608	,009	Sig

Source: Research data are processed, 2019

Hypothesis

The hypotheses of this have five hypotheses. Based on Table five, the conclusions the five hypotheses are: The effects of examining have an effect on of exertions intrinsic work engagement recommend that social art work values have an effect on work engagement. The effects of examining the effect of work rate on art work engagement recommend that art work rate influences art work engagement. The effects of examining the effect of art work values on art work engagement recommend that art work fame does now not have an effect on engagement. Also, the effects of attempting out the effect of on art work engagement recommend that work engagement influences work engagement

DISCUSSION

The discussion about generation Y becomes very interesting when it is associated with characteristics, problems, and parties encountered to deal with these problems. The results of this study itself show that the characteristics of generation Y, in general, can be categorized into two, namely positive and negative characteristics. Generation Y, with all its positive and negative characteristics, has various problems, namely gadget addiction, not focusing on learning, easily distracted emotions, pornography, and promiscuity.

Generation Y when faced with problems tends to discuss with peers and parents. Surprisingly, when they face a problem, they do not tend to discuss it with counselors, psychologists, or academic advisory lecturers. Since the role of Generation Y in determining how to add value to work is very important, involving Generation Y in work is necessary to make work more valuable. Basically, the aim is to increase the value of the work from a cognitive, instrumental,

and social perspective, further enhancing the prestige dimension. Adding value to your work is not easy, as it requires organizational commitment and a strategy supported by Gen Y.

The variables in this survey play a very important position. The Organizational Engagement variable has the best index value associated with Generation Y. This forms the basis for leading Generation Y managers in the workplace. And based on the results of this study, it is expected that the company will pay attention to the work value of employees in generation Y and take action steps to create programs that can increase the work value of generation Y. Likewise for organizational commitment to generation Y, the company should conduct an in-depth analysis related to the following aspects: aspects related to generation Y.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The purpose of this look at turned to discover solutions to the studies questions posed in this look at. Namely, "associated with Generation Y's organizational dedication with the aid of using growing the fee of paintings." The outcomes of this look at substantiate studies questions that result in several, and offer conclusions that answer succinctly. Work may be extended from a cognitive, instrumental, and social perspective, similarly improving the status size.

To make jobs greater valuable, we want to have interaction Generation Y. This is due to the fact whilst Gen Y is deeply worried in an organization, Gen Y's dedication to. May be the muse of the paintings of Gen Y managers, mainly in the virtual age. Study obstacles derived from this look at are, this look at effective analyzed the problem of organizational engagement with the aid of using in Generation Y. However, it has not been checked out from different that you to produce studies that give an explanation for factor of the elements that boom. The outcomes and located obstacles of this look at constitute a supply of thoughts and input for destiny. Among different things, it's far recommended that this look expanded.

REFERENCES

- ❖ Angeline, T. (2011). Addressing Generational Diversity in the Workplace : Expectations and Perceptions of Different Generations of Employees. *African Journal of Business Administration*, 5(2), 249-255. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJBM10.335>
- ❖ Berkup, p. B (2014). Generation Z operating with Generation X and Generation Y Period:Management of various generations in business. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences* MCSER Publishing, 5(19),20399340. <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2014.v5n19p218>
- ❖ Broadbridge, A. M., Maxwell, GA, and Ogden, SM. (2007). 13_2_30's Experiences, Perceptions, and Expectations for Gen Y Retail Employment. *Career Development International*, 12(6), 523–544. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13620430710822001>
- ❖ Davis, E. (2016). Job Value Priorities for Millennial Students.
- ❖ Ferdinand, A. (2014). *Management Research Act* (fifth ed.). Semarang:Diponegoro University Press.
- ❖ Gallup. (2016). How millennials need to paintings and stay by Chairman and CEO.
- ❖ Ghozali, I. (2016). *Application of multivariate evaluation with the IBM SPSS 23 program* (eighth edition). Semarang:Diponegoro University Press.

- ❖ Gursoy, D., Chi, C.G.Q., & Karadag, E. (2013).Generational variations in paintings values and attitudes of frontline and carrier touch workers. *International Journal of Hotel Management*, 32(1), 40–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2012.04.002>
- ❖ Lyon, p. T., Higgins, CA, and Duxbury, L. (2010). Value of Work:Development of latest third-dimensional systems primarily based totally on confirmatory small-area evaluation. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 31, 969-1002.<https://doi.org/10.1002/job>
- ❖ Lyons, S. T., Schweitzer, L., Ng, E. S. W., & Kuron,
- ❖ L. K. (2010). J (2012). An apple-to-apple comparison:A qualitative take a look at of occupational migration styles throughout 4 generations. *Career Development International*,17(4), 333357.<https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/MRR-09-2015-0216>
- ❖ McCrindle, M. (2006) 。 New Generations at Work:Attracting, Recruiting, Retraining, and Training Generation Y. McCrindle Research.
- ❖ Meier, J., Austin, S.F., & Crocker, M. (2010).Generation Y withinside the Workforce:Leadership Challenges. *Journal of Human Resources and Adult Learning*, 6 (1991), 68-79.
- ❖ Papavasileiou, E.F. & Lyons, S. T (2015). A comparative evaluation of the exertions price of Greek 'millennials'. *InternationalJournal of Human Resources Management*, 26(17),21662186.<https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2014.985325>
- ❖ Robbins, S. (2013) withinside the *Journal of Experimental Science and Theoretical Physics*. <https://doi.org/10.12737/4477>
- ❖ Sajjadi, A., Sun, B., & Castillo, C. (2010). A(2012). Generational variations in consciousness of paintings.
- ❖ Sebastian, Y., Amran, D. & Youth Lab. (2016).*LanggasGeneration:Millennials Indonesia*. Jakarta:media ideas.
- ❖ Sekaran, U. (2006). *Research Methodology for Business*(4th ed.). Jakarta:Salemba Empat.
- ❖ Sillerud, H. (2011).Generational Differences in Workers'Work Values - An Exploratory Study withinside the Norwegian Work Context.
- ❖ Smora, K. W. & Sutton, CD (2002). GenerationDifferences:Revised Labor Values for New Millennium Generations.*Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 23 (SPEC. ISS.),363382.<https://doi.org/10.1002/job.147>
- ❖ Sorttheix, F.M., Chow, A., & Salmela-Aro, K.(2015).Work Values and Transitions to Work Life:A Longitudinal Study .*Journal of Professional Behavior*, 89, 162–171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2015.06.001>
- ❖ Twenge, J.M. (2010). A overview of empirical proof for generational variations in attitudes to paintings. *Journal of Economics and Psychology*, 25(2), 201–210. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-010-9165-6>